

in solution in meq/100 ml, and a and b are constants. The slopes for the different acids were in the order, butyric > formic > propionic > tartaric = succinic > acetic for Tulsion WB, and butyric > formic = propionic > tartaric for De Acidite HIP (Fig. 1).

Two more aspects of this study are also presented here.

Total uptake of organic acids by weak base anion-exchange resins in the hydroxide forms: It was found that the total uptake of monobasic organic acids by hydroxide forms of these two gel-type anion-exchange resins was in the order, butyric > propionic > acetic. This is in accordance with the results obtained by Robinson and Mills⁵ in their studies with the uptake of aliphatic acids by Duolite A-2 anion-exchange resin. The data also reveal that uptake of dibasic acids was in the sequence, oxalic > tartaric > succinic. The higher uptake of formic acid over the other monobasic acids, viz. acetic and propionic may be attributed to its high ionisation constant, 1.76×10^{-4} . Similarly, the higher uptake of oxalic and tartaric acids over that of succinic acid can be explained by their higher ionisation constants.

It was observed in the experiment that physical adsorption of oxalic acid was 0.7 meq/g dry resin for Tulsion WB and 0.2 meq/g dry resin for De Acidite HIP. Thus, these resins exhibited a capacity higher than their theoretical values when equilibrated with oxalic acid.

The higher uptake of citric acid on De Acidite HIP may be due to its physical adsorption. It is seen from the experiment that physical adsorption of this acid was 0.7 meq/g dry resin. Thus it can be concluded that the ionisation constant of organic acids plays an important role in their uptake by gel-type anion-exchange resins⁹. The magnitude of the effect of ionisation constant increases as the basicity of the resin decreases.

Uptake of organic acids by different forms of anion-exchange resins: It has been reported⁹ that relative ease of replacement of the various anions depends on valence, ion size and strength of acids formed by the anion, and that hydroxyl ion has a unique position in anion-exchange resins, e.g. hydroxyl ions exhibit an exceedingly high exchange potential. It is clear from the results presented that both the weakly basic anion-exchange resins under study have high exchange potential in their hydroxide forms over the chloride and sulphate forms in case of all the organic acids studied here. A similar observation was made by Trivedi⁹ during his studies on exchange equilibria of different anions on anion-exchange resins. It is for this reason of high exchange potential that effect of the concentration and rate of uptake have been studied here using hydroxide forms of both the resins.

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Stability Constants of 2*N*-3,5-Dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole Complexes with Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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IN the present communication the dissociation constant of the 2*N*-3,5-dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole and formation constant of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Bjerrum-Calvin^{1,2} pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³ at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at various ionic strengths in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The appropriate correction in all pH-meter readings were made on account of solvent as suggested by Van Uitert and Haas⁴.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligand: The ligand 2*N*-3,5-dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1) was prepared by refluxing the equimolar quantities of 2-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole with 3,5-dibromosalicylaldehyde in absolute alcohol for 3 h on a water-bath and was repeatedly crystallised in dioxane to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 218° (Found: C, 41.00; S, 7.00; N, 9.56. Calcd. C, 41.00; S, 7.28; N, 9.56%).

Materials: All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Standard solutions of copper sulphate and nickel sulphate were prepared in conductivity water.

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NOTES

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANT AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Metals	Ionic strength	$\mu = 0.05$			$\mu = 0.10$			$\mu = 0.15$		
		I	II	III	I	II	III	I	II	III
	$\log K_1^H$	6.95*			6.89			6.75		
		6.90**			6.80			6.80		
Cu ^{II}	$\log K_1$	6.84	6.80	7.19	6.99	—	7.08	6.58	6.52	6.82
	$\log K_2$	6.28	6.24	5.94	5.96	—	5.96	6.08	6.02	5.76
	$\log \beta_n$	18.12	18.04	18.18	12.95	—	12.99	12.66	12.54	12.58
Ni ^{II}	$\log K_1$	5.98	—	5.98	4.96	4.90	5.28	5.16	4.82	5.11
	$\log K_2$	4.62	—	4.72	4.42	4.86	4.21	3.78	3.44	3.88
	$\log \beta_n$	10.60	—	10.65	9.38	9.26	9.49	8.94	8.26	8.99

* Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values. ** Linear plot method. I = Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values II = mid-point method, III = interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values.

The metal contents were estimated by standard methods⁵. The solution of 2N-3,5-dibromosalicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (DBSPT) was prepared in dioxane. The carbonate-free NaOH solution was prepared in conductivity water and used in potentiometric titrations. Stock solutions of sodium perchlorate (neutral) and perchloric acid were prepared in conductivity water.

A Elico Lt-10 pH meter having glass and saturated calomel electrode was used for the titrations. The pH meter was calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (pH 4.05).

Results

Proton ligand stability constant : In the ligand, it is the phenolic OH group that takes part in the complex formation and proton is replaced from it by the metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, the number of dissociable protons, Y, attached to ligand molecule is one.

Calculation of proton ligand stability constants was carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}H$ against pH and the value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}H=0.5$. The plot of $\log(\bar{n}H/1-\bar{n}H)$ vs pH was also drawn. From this pK_2 was evaluated. This value agrees quite well with that obtained by half-integral method (Table 1).

Metal ligand stability constant : The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} systems were determined by half-integral method plotting the $\bar{n}$ values against pL. These values were further confirmed by the various computational method⁶, viz. interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, mid-point method and interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values.

Discussion

As the ionic strength increases the values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ decrease. This observation is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel⁷ equation. The observed order of stability for the above metal

ions is Cu^{II} > Ni^{II}, and conforms to Irving-Williams⁸ order of stability.

The formation of six-membered ring complex has created a very unusual features in the compound, i.e. a six- and five-membered ring is alternate to each other predicting the high stability which has actually been observed by the experimental data. Another phenomenon observed in the ligand molecule is the appearance of conjugated double and single bond in the formation of metal chelates which is also responsible for the higher stability data.

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Synthesis of D-Glycero-D-galactoheptose

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IN 1945 Sowden and Fischer¹ reacted aldoses with nitromethane in the presence of sodium methoxide to form the corresponding nitroalcohols which were then subjected to the Nef reaction². In the Nef reaction an aqueous solution of the sodium nitroalcohol is added to a moderately concentrated sulphuric acid solution when the next higher aldose is formed together with sodium bisulphate with the evolution of nitrous oxide. Using this synthesis